

T.R.
GEBZE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES

**DEVELOPMENT OF A UNIFORM MAGNETIC FIELD
GENERATOR FOR MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING
APPLICATIONS**

YAVUZ ÖZTÜRK
**A THESIS SUBMITTED FOR THE DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS**

GEBZE
2017

T.R.
GEBZE TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES

**DEVELOPMENT OF A UNIFORM
MAGNETIC FIELD GENERATOR FOR
MAGNETIC RESONANCE APPLICATIONS**

YAVUZ ÖZTÜRK

**A THESIS SUBMITTED FOR THE DEGREE OF
DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS**

THESIS SUPERVISOR
PROF. DR. BULAT Z. RAMĪ

GEBZE
2017

T.C.
GEBZE TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
FEN BİLİMLERİ ENSTİTÜSÜ

MANYETİK REZONANS
GÖRÜNTÜLEME İÇİN HOMOJEN
MANYETİK ALAN ÜRETECİ
GELİŞTİRİLMESİ

YAVUZ ÖZTÜRK
DOKTORA TEZİ
FİZİK ANABİLİM DALI

DANIŞMANI
PROF. DR. BULAT Z. RAMİ

GEBZE

2017

GEBZE TEKNİK ÜNİVERSİTESİ

DOKTORA JÜRİ ONAY FORMU

GTÜ Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Yönetim Kurulu'nun 22/03/2017 tarih ve 2017/18 sayılı kararıyla oluşturulan jüri tarafından 07/04/2017 tarihinde tez savunma sınavı yapılan Yavuz Öztürk'ün tez çalışması Fizik Anabilim Dalında DOKTORA tezi olarak kabul edilmiştir.

JÜRİ

ÜYE

(TEZ DANIŞMANI) : Prof. Dr. Bulat Z. RAMİ

ÜYE

: Doç. Dr. Georgy MOZZHUKHIN

ÜYE

: Prof. Dr. Kemal ÖZDOĞAN

ÜYE

: Yrd. Doç. Dr. Cengiz OKAY

ÜYE:

: Yrd. Doç. Dr. Sinan KAZAN

ONAY

Gebze Teknik Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü Yönetim Kurulu'nun

...../...../..... tarih ve/..... sayılı kararı.

İMZA/MÜHÜR

SUMMARY

In this thesis work, we have investigated possible structures for generating uniform magnetic fields. As an introduction, we gave an overall picture of the uniform magnetic field generation literature. In the second part, we worked on several different candidate structures for uniform magnetic field generation, and we have concluded that, spheroidal surfaces – which have been revealed in theoretical analysis, and later confirmed by FEA results – are very promising for practical applications. For making use of the advantages of spheroidal surfaces, firstly a constant ampere per turn ratio along the principle axis of a spheroid was studied for uniform magnetic field generation therein. Later, a continuous winding structure, which is easier to realize in practice – a spheroidal helical coil – have been proposed and modelled by FEA calculations. Our results suggest that, uniformity of at least 20 ppm within 75% of a whole spheroidal volume and 50 ppm uniformity within 90% of it are in fact achievable.

In the final part of the thesis, we have focused on the production of such a coil and a method has been proposed, applied and experimental measurements were conducted on the prototype. For that, a computer aided design (CAD) of an air-cored spheroidal coil was performed a priori, using the formulation; and a coil template was produced, employing a commercial off the shelf, affordable, 3D desktop printer; inasmuch as it is virtually impossible via conventional production techniques. The coil has been finalized using this template, and the magnetic field created inside employing a current source was measured by a Hall probe through holes which have been intentionally left on the template. Our measurements agree with the finite element results and show a good magnetic field uniformity therein. We have achieved a field uniformity of around 1% experimentally, although numerical analysis pointed out the possibility of 20 ppm uniformity. Thus, the developed spheroidal surface coil can be improved by following a more accurate manufacturing process.

Key Words: Uniform Magnetic Field, Helical Coil, Surface Coils, 3D printing, Spheroid.

ÖZET

Bu tez çalışmasında, düzgün manyetik alanlar üretilmesine yönelik olası yapıların araştırması yapılmıştır. Girişte, düzgün manyetik alan üretimi literatürünün genel bir resmi verilmiştir. İkinci bölümde, düzgün manyetik alan üretimi için öne çıkan birkaç farklı aday yapı üzerinde durulmuş, akabinde sonlu eleman analizlerimize ve analitik sonuçlarımıza bağlı olarak, sferoid helezonik sargı adını verdiğimiz, üretilebilecek nihai bir yapı önerilmiştir. Hesaplamalardan elde edilen sonuçlar, tüm iç hacmin %75'inde en az 20 ppm'lik ve %90'ında ise 50 ppm'lik bir manyetik alan düzgünlüğünün elde edilebilir olduğunu göstermiştir. Tezimizin son bölümünde ise, bu yapının üretimi üzerinde durulmuştur. Hava çekirdekli sferoid sargının üretilmesine yönelik, türettiğimiz formül kullanılarak bir bilgisayar destekli tasarım (CAD) çalışması gerçekleştirilmiş; rafta hazır ticari ve uygun fiyatlı bir 3-Boyutlu masaüstü yazıcı kullanılarak bir sarım kalıbı üretilmiştir. Böylece geleneksel üretim teknikleri ile neredeyse imkânsız olan sargı gerçekleştirilebilmiştir. Sargı bir akım kaynağı tarafından sürülmüş ve içerisindeki manyetik alan, kalıp üzerinde hususi olarak bırakılmış deliklerden bir Hall probu vasıtasıyla ölçülmüştür. Ölçümlerimiz son derece düzgün bir manyetik alan gösteren sonlu elemanlar sonuçlarıyla iyi bir uyum içerisinde olmuştur. Bununla birlikte, numerik analizler 20 ppm'lik alan düzgünlüğüne işaret etmiş olmasına rağmen deneysel olarak ancak %1'lik manyetik alan düzgünlüğü seviyelerine ulaşılabilmektedir. Bu ise, daha hassas bir imalat süreci izlendiği takdirde, sonuçlardaki başarının çok daha öteye taşınabileceğini göstermesi açısından önemlidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Düzgün Manyetik Alan, Helis Sargı, Yüzey Sargısı, 3B yazıcı, Sferoid.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In my opinion the most difficult part of writing a thesis is acknowledgements part. Because, many of my friends and colleagues supported and encouraged me during my work. I want to apologize to those whom I have not mentioned here name by name and I would like to express my deep and sincere gratitude to my supervisors, my colleagues and to my family for their everlasting support and patience. And especially to Magnomech for their unceasing support in 3D printing.

TABLE of CONTENTS

	<u>Page</u>
SUMMARY	v
ÖZET	vi
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	vii
TABLE OF CONTENTS	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	xi
LIST OF TABLES	xvii
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Solenoidal Coils	1
1.2. Helmholtz Coils	3
1.3. Other Structures	8
2. THESIS PURPOSE AND CONTRIBUTION	10
3. POLYNOMIAL COILS	12
3.1. Paraboloid Coil Structure	12
3.2. Linearly Changing Coil Structure	16
3.3. General Solution	19
4. SOLENOIDS WITH CHANGING PROFILE	21
4.1. Solenoid with Compensation Coils at the Ends	21
4.2. Discrete Solenoids with Changing Outside Diameters	25
4.2.1. Discrete Solenoid: Design 1	26
4.2.2. Discrete Solenoid: Design 2	28
5. SPHEROIDAL SHELL STRUCTURES	32
5.1. Spherical Shells	32
5.1.1. Closed Spherical Shell	32
5.1.2. Spherical Arc Shell	34
5.2. Spheroidal Shells	38
5.2.1. Elliptical Shell	38
5.2.2. Truncated Elliptic Shell (Prolate)	41
5.2.3. Truncated Elliptic Shell (Oblate)	43
5.2.4. Truncated Concentric-Ellipsoidal Shell	45

6. SPHEROIDAL COILS	48
6.1. Surface Current Density for a Uniform Field therein	48
6.2. Current Rings	51
6.3. The Winding Function	53
6.4. The Spheroidal Helical Coil	56
7. DESIGN AND PRODUCTION	61
8. MEASUREMENTS	66
8.1. Method	66
8.2. Results and Discussion	67
9. CONCLUSION	70
REFERENCES	70
BIOGRAPHY	75
APPENDICES	76

LIST of ABBREVIATIONS and ACRONYMS

<u>Symbols and Abbreviations</u>	<u>Explanations</u>
2D	: Two Dimensional
3D	: Three Dimensional
CAD	: Computer Aided Design
CST	: Computer Simulation Solutions
DC	: Direct Current
EM	: Electromagnetic
EPR	: Electron Paramagnetic Resonance
ESR	: Electron Spin Resonance
FEA	: Finite Element Analysis
FDM	: Fused Deposition Molding
FMR	: Ferromagnetic Resonance
FMRI	: Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
MR	: Magnetic Resonance
MRI	: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NMR	: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
ppm	: parts per million
RF	: Radio Frequency

LIST of FIGURES

<u>Figure No:</u>	<u>Page</u>
1.1: Magnetic field lines of a cylindrical coil.	2
1.2: Magnetic field strength along the axis of a cylindrical coil.	2
1.3: A Helmholtz coil pair is illustrated. The distance between two coil rings is equal to the coil radius. This radius value is the so-called Helmholtz radius.	3
1.4: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to the central field value in terms of the Helmholtz radius R within $\pm R/10$ range. The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.	4
1.5: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to the central value in terms of Helmholtz radius R within $\pm R/4$ range. The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.	5
1.6: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to central value in terms of Helmholtz radius R within whole range ($\pm R/2$). The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.	5
1.7: Schematic arrangement of a Ruben coil.	6
1.8: Schematic arrangement of a three-coil Merritt system.	7
1.9: Schematic arrangement of a four-coil Merritt system.	8
1.10: Schematic of a pair of Saddle Coils.	8
3.1: The Paraboloid coil.	12
3.2: Parametric definition of the problem in CST EM Studio is illustrated.	14
3.3: Paraboloid coil defined in CST EM Studio.	15
3.4: Simulation results for different a and b parameter values.	15
3.5: Linearly changing coil profile defined in CST EM Studio.	17
3.6: Simulation results for different parameters.	18
3.7: Results for parameters $n=12$ and $n=15$ are shown.	20
4.1: The sketch of the solenoid with compensation coils at the ends.	22
4.2: Multi-coil geometry.	22
4.3: The Multi-coil and the parametrization in CST Studio.	23

4.4:	Resultant magnetic field lines of the structure.	23
4.5:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the coil is plotted.	24
4.6:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.	24
4.7:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis.	25
4.8:	The coil sketch of Design 1.	26
4.9:	Coil model of Design 1 in Solidworks.	26
4.10:	The definition of the problem in CST Studio (Design 1).	27
4.11:	The resulting magnetic field lines in Design 1.	27
4.12:	The magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted.	27
4.13:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.	28
4.14:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis	28
4.15:	The coil sketch of Design 2.	29
4.16:	Coil model of Design 2 in Solidworks.	29
4.17:	The definition of the problem in CST Studio (Design 2).	30
4.18:	The resulting magnetic field lines in Design 2.	30
4.19:	The magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted.	30
4.20:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.	31
4.21:	The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis.	31
5.1:	Schematic description of the Spherical Shell Coil is illustrated. The red straight line indicates the region where we have calculated the field uniformity.	32
5.2:	Parametric definition of Spherical Shell Coil in CST.	33
5.3:	Magnetic field lines for the Spherical Shell Coil.	33
5.4:	Calculations showed that magnetic field uniformity is around 1.1 % on the ± 50 mm central line (the red line in Figure 5.1).	33

5.5:	Schematic description of the spherical arcs, which created a spherical arc shell is illustrated. The red and the green lines are the regions for magnetic field uniformity calculation.	34
5.6:	Cross-sectional view of the Spherical Arc Shell Coil.	34
5.7:	Parametric definition of Spherical Shell Arc Coil.	35
5.8:	Magnetic field lines for the Spherical Shell Arc Coil.	35
5.9:	Magnitude of the magnetic field is plotted on the xy plane. Here the star-like central region corresponds to 400 ppm homogeneity.	36
5.10:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.	36
5.11:	Magnetic field magnitude on the green line in Figure 5.5 is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is around 40 ppm.	36
5.12:	Magnetic field magnitude along the lateral line passing through the coil center is plotted.	37
5.13:	Magnetic field magnitude on the red line in Figure 5.5 is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is around 30 ppm.	37
5.14:	Schematic description of the elliptic shell.	38
5.15:	Prolate ellipsoidal shell coil cross-section as seen in CST Studio.	39
5.16:	Parametric definition of the prolate ellipsoidal shell problem.	39
5.17:	Resultant magnetic field lines of the prolate ellipsoidal shell structure.	39
5.18:	Magnitude of the magnetic field is plotted on the xy plane. Here the star-like central region corresponds to 400 ppm homogeneity.	40
5.19:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the prolate ellipsoidal coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.	40
5.20:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 40 ppm.	40
5.21:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 13 ppm.	41
5.22:	Parametric definition of the truncated prolate ellipsoidal shell problem	42
5.23:	Resultant magnetic field lines of the truncated prolate ellipsoidal shell structure.	42

5.24:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the prolate ellipsoidal coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.	42
5.25:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 40 ppm.	43
5.26:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. The Magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 40 ppm.	43
5.27:	Parametric definition of the oblate ellipsoidal shell problem.	44
5.28:	Resultant magnetic field lines of the oblate ellipsoidal shell structure.	44
5.29:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted. The magnetic field is less uniform compared to the prolate structure.	44
5.30:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 150 ppm.	45
5.31:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. Magnetic field homogeneity was calculated to be 360 ppm.	45
5.32:	Parametric definition of the concentric-ellipsoidal shell problem.	46
5.33:	The resultant magnetic field lines of the concentric-ellipsoidal shell structure.	46
5.34:	Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the concentric-ellipsoidal structure.	47
5.35:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 187 ppm.	47
5.36:	Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis is plotted. Magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 422 ppm.	47
6.1:	a) The spheroid dimensions and b) the axes.	52
6.2:	The current carrying rings on a prolate spheroid is illustrated.	52

6.3:	a) The spheroidal surface current rings structure modeled in CST EM Studio. Small arrows indicated the direction of the current. b) Cross-sectional view of the meshed structure is on the right.	52
6.4:	Magnetic field along the principal axis., Field uniformity = 0.03%.	53
6.5:	Magnetic field along the lateral axis, Field uniformity = 0.03%.	53
6.6:	Constant pitch spheroidal surface coil, the spheroid geometry and the spheroidal formula in cylindrical coordinate system.	54
6.7:	The magnetostatic problem in CST EM Studio: a) The helical spheroidal coil and the current path for the flow. The path is ranging between ± 250 mm in z, and between 0-250 mm in y directions. b) The computational region is selected to be large enough to minimize the effects from the boundaries.	57
6.8:	2-dimensional view of the problem is illustrated. Construction of the magnetostatic problem in CST EM Studio: a) The helical spheroidal coil, the current path and the boundaries. b) The mesh structure used in the problem is tetrahedral and contains 312,062 tetrahedrons which are demonstrated here.	58
6.9:	Magnetic field plotted in the yz plane (units are in Tesla (V.s/m ²)).	58
6.10:	The three components of the magnetic field along the major axis.	59
6.11:	The three components of the magnetic field along one of the minor axes.	59
6.12:	Magnetic field uniformity in the a) xy b) xz and c) yz planes.	60
7.1:	A cross-sectional view of a lab-size spheroidal helical coil designed in <i>BS Solidworks</i> software.	61
7.2:	A general view of a lab-size uniform magnetic field generator.	62
7.3:	a) The template designed in Solidworks b) A cross-sectional view of the template c) & d) An illustration of the process of copper wire winding on the template.	63
7.4:	3D Builder.	64
7.5:	3D printing technique based on fused deposition molding (FDM): 1 – Plastic filament is ejected molten from the nozzle, 2 – Material is deposited, 3 – Below there is a controlled movable table to control the material deposition.	64

7.6:	a) The two semi-spheroids of the template, printed using FDM method:	65
	b) The wire wound on the two parts of the template, the contact gasket between the pieces is shown in the inset; c) & d) Assembled spheroidal helical surface coil.	
8.1:	The measurement setup of the spheroidal helical surface coil, consisting of a Hirst GM05 Gaussmeter and GW Instek GPS 4303 DC power supply, is shown. Measurements are done through the holes of the coil template using the transverse Hall probe of the gaussmeter.	66
8.2:	A closer view of the setup.	67
8.3:	Magnetic field measurements inside the spheroidal coil along the major axis.	68
8.4:	Magnetic field measurements inside the spheroidal coil in the lateral direction.	68

LIST of TABLES

<u>Table No:</u>	<u>Page</u>
3.1: Coil parameters used for simulations in CST.	15
3.2: Magnetic field uniformity within ± 50 mm central region.	16
3.3: Winding parameters.	17
3.4: Magnetic field uniformity within ± 50 mm central region.	17
3.5 Coil parameters and corresponding field deviations.	19
4.1: Axial and radial magnetic field homogeneity.	25
4.2: Design 1, windings.	26
4.3: Design 2, windings.	29

1. INTRODUCTION

Generating uniform magnetic fields¹, which is crucial for many technological applications, is continuing to be an important issue of the basic physics and still drawing attention of the scientific community. In fact, for a magnetic measurement device to work properly and a measurement to be meaningful, operational magnetic fields must be calibrated accurately, otherwise any information derived would be meaningless. Indeed, many magnetic measurement devices such as magnetometers [1], susceptometers [2], eddy current probes [3], magnetic calibrators [4, 5], magnetic traps [6]; and magnetic resonance measuring instruments of any kind (NMR, FMR, ESR, EPR etc.) depend on a certain level of uniformity in their operational magnetic fields. For instance, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) instruments need field uniformity to be as high as possible (< 5 ppm) along with extreme field intensities (ranging from 0.1 to 3 T)². Here, this high homogeneity and magnitude of static magnetic field are desired for detecting the MRI signals from different portions of a subject body with an enhanced imaging resolution [8].

There are several methods for uniform magnetic field generation some of which are conventional, others are gaining ground. Below you will find a brief review of some of these methods.

1.1. Solenoidal Coils

The most simple and conventional way of producing a uniform magnetic field is realized by winding a long cylindrical coil, which is also called a solenoidal coil (Figure 1.1 - picture is taken from [9]). It is well-known that an infinite cylindrical coil has a perfectly aligned magnetic field inside along its axis, which is equal to $n\mu_0 I$ in magnitude, where n is the number of windings, I is the current and μ_0 is the permeability of the free space [10].

Regarding a cylindrical coil of finite length, it is also possible to obtain uniform magnetic fields to some extent, at the center of the coil, i.e. away from its ends (Figure

¹ Throughout this thesis, magnetic field uniformity and homogeneity are used synonymously.

² Field magnitude may rise to 7 T in the case of Functional MRIs (fMRI) [7].

1.2 - picture is taken from [10]). However, building a coil having a high aspect ratio is not always practical. On the other hand, truncation of the coil causes deflections and inhomogeneity in the magnetic field. This can be compensated to some extent through some additional windings at both ends. This possibility will be discussed later in this thesis. In fact, such extra elements constitute the ground of shimming techniques used not only in solenoidal coils for compensating field inhomogeneity. These techniques are widely used in various branches of magnetic resonance (MR) and MRI techniques [7].

Figure 1.1: Magnetic field lines of a cylindrical coil.

Figure 1.2: Magnetic field strength along the axis of a cylindrical coil.

1.2. Helmholtz Coils

- Standard Helmholtz Coils

Helmholtz coils – named after its inventor, the German physicist Hermann von Helmholtz – are the most widely used and practical devices for producing uniform magnetic fields [2, 11-17]. A standard Helmholtz coil consists of a pair of equivalent circular coil loops having radius R . These two loops are placed parallel to each other aligned on a line and apart from each other at the same distance R (Figure 1.3 - picture is taken from [18]). This common R value is called the “Helmholtz radius”. Keeping the distance between pairs equal to the Helmholtz radius value, minimizes non-uniformity of the field at the center of the structure. The second derivative (i.e. the second order term in the polynomial expansion) of the magnetic field vanishes in the case of an ideal Helmholtz coil pair, which leaves the first nonzero derivative to be the fourth derivative, in expense of worsening the uniformity of the field at the off-axis space of the system [19-20].

Figure 1.3: A Helmholtz coil pair is illustrated. The distance between two coil rings is equal to the coil radius. This radius value is the so-called Helmholtz radius.

Helmholtz coils can generate satisfactory uniform magnetic fields in relatively large volumes for various applications. However, magnetic field uniformity which can be attained by their utilization has certain limits (especially dimensional). One handicap is the existence of the uniformity only around the center which is small

compared to the overall volume being occupied. That is a situation which restricted out-of-lab utilization of the Helmholtz coils.

As an example, considering a displacement of one tenth of the Helmholtz radius off the center, one can see a deviation of about 0.01% from the central field value [21] (see also Figure 1.4). This corresponds to 100 ppm field uniformity within a virtual central sphere having radius R/10. This is actually a very small portion of the effective space occupied by the whole cylindrical Helmholtz structure:

$$\frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi(R/10)^3}{\pi R^2 R} = \frac{1}{750} \quad (1.1)$$

corresponding to a small ratio of only about 0.13%.

Figure 1.4: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to the central field value in terms of the Helmholtz radius R within $\pm R/10$ range. The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.

For a larger displacement at the center, such as R/4, uniformity assumed is no better than 0.5% (Figure 1.5), which may still be sufficient for some applications,

$$\frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi(R/4)^3}{\pi R^2 R} = \frac{1}{48} \quad (1.2)$$

where the usable volume ratio in this case increases to 2%.

Figure 1.5: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to the central value in terms of Helmholtz radius R within $\pm R/4$ range. The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.

Figure 1.6: FEA results demonstrated the change in the magnetic field strength with respect to central value in terms of Helmholtz radius R within whole range ($\pm R/2$). The magnetic field value at the center is normalized to 100.

Considering the whole central line the magnetic field uniformity is almost vanished. Here the change is as much as 6% (Figure 1.6).

- Ruben Coils

There are several revisions to the standard Helmholtz design for enlarging either the central homogeneous region of magnetization or the field quality itself [22]. Ruben coils [23], for instance, are constructed using five square coils each with specified ampere-turn ratios proportional to the numbers 19, 4, 10, 4, 19 respectively, all situated at equal distances from one another. These ampere-turn ratios can easily be achieved by providing necessary number of windings. The distance between two adjacent wires are equal to one fourth of the cubic edge (Figure 1.7). Another advantage of the design is its utilization of square coils instead of circular ones. Square coils are known to have two significant advantages over the circular ones. One of these advantages is their easy construction; the other is their better accessibility [24]. The coils can be constructed on the outer or inner surfaces of a cubic structure, like a chamber and can be walked through easily. Regarding the central uniformity (the 100-ppm region), the region is enlarged by a factor of 2.5 in a Ruben coil compared to that of a standard Helmholtz coil [22].

Figure 1.7: Schematic arrangement of a Ruben coil.

- Merritt Coils

Merritt et al. offered four and three square coils versions which outperformed Ruben coils [25]. They adopted a direct analytical approach for determining design parameters of the coils by considering the Taylor expansion for the axial field and calculated optimal dimensions for the coils. For maximization of the on-axis homogeneity of the magnetic field, $B(x)$, as many as possible terms in the expansion

must vanish at the center. Since $B(x)$ is an even function because of the system symmetry, only even terms exist in the Taylor expansion. It turns out that, it is possible to eliminate up to the fourth order term using three-coils version of the Merritt coils. The four-coils version gives even the possibility to eliminate up to the sixth order term. That is, to achieve a better homogeneity compared to that of the three-coil version.

The three-coil Merritt system geometry is constructed over a rectangular prism having dimensions $d \times d \times s$ where a pair of identical coils straddle a middle coil equilaterally (Figure 1.8). The most uniform field distribution was obtained with ratios $s/d = 0.821116$ and $I_1/I_2 = 0.512797$, latter being the ratio of currents.

The four-coil Merritt system is constructed using two pairs of twin coils. The inner coils are situated equilaterally from the center by a distance a and the outer ones by a distance b ($b > a$). In that combination, the best uniformity is obtained for ratios $a/d = 0.128106$ and $b/d = 0.505492$. The ratio of the currents in the inner pair of coils to that of the outer pair is be $I_1/I_2 = 0.423514$ (Figure 1.9).

Figure 1.8: Schematic arrangement of a three-coil Merritt system.

Figure 1.9: Schematic arrangement of a four-coil Merritt system.

Other Helmholtz-like coil structures are also proposed for enhancing the field uniformity or strength. There are systems which consist of three [26, 27], four [28-30] or even larger number of coils in diverse combinations [31, 32].

1.3. Other Structures

- Saddle Coils

Another method for uniform magnetic field generation is using saddle coils [33-35]. Saddle-coils (Figure 1.10) are often used for producing laterally aligned uniform RF magnetic fields, which are perpendicular to a vertically applied static magnetic field of a solenoid. Such a coil can be constructed using the outer surface of a cylindrical frame and made easily accessible from outside.

Figure 1.10: Schematic of a pair of Saddle Coils.

The magnetic field inside such a structure can be calculated using the Biot-Savart law and the field can be expressed in Taylor series expansion with all odd components vanishing because of symmetry. Besides, the second-order terms for a saddle coil have no y or z component at the origin (z being the cylindrical axis).

- Ellipsoidal Bodies

Another method for obtaining uniform magnetic fields is using an ellipsoidal structure. It is long well-known that ellipsoidal magnetic bodies can be used to generate uniform magnetic fields inside [36-39]. Since for a closed surface one can always find a surface current distribution which yields a magnetic field inside thereof as is produced by an outer source [40]; in the case the surface is of an ellipsoid, a uniform magnetic field inside can always be produced using certain surface current profiles. Regarding a spheroid (an ellipsoid of rotation), which corresponds to the one-fold degeneracy of the general ellipsoid principal dimensions, the surface current distribution is known to have a uniform turns density along its major axis [41, 42]. This is unsurprisingly true for a spherical surface, which represents the limiting case of a rotational ellipsoid [43-51].

- Cos(θ) Coils

Cos θ coils are used for obtaining laterally uniform magnetic fields inside a cylindrical body [43].

- Other Alternatives

Alternative methods employing planar currents [52, 53], line currents [54] are also proposed. This is based on generating novel self-shielding polyhedral structures of surface currents. The field generated by these structures is perpendicular to the main axis of the cavity, which is not the case in conventional helical coils. By this method, the structure can be analyzed with an exact mathematical model. Similar principles are applied for permanent magnet structures as well for uniform magnetic field generation [55, 56].

2. THESIS PURPOSE AND CONTRIBUTION

This thesis is focused on generating uniform magnetic fields for diverse applications, e.g. for MR applications. We have pursued both analytical calculations and FEA calculations using CST Studio software package. Some of the results are also confirmed using COMSOL Multiphysics. As the result of these theoretical studies, we have chosen a specific design to produce a uniform magnetic field. Consequently, we have developed and applied methods for producing such structures. We have proposed and employed a 3D printing method, which enables realization of almost all kind of surface coils, not only for uniform magnetic field generation but also for other purposes such as gradient magnetic field generation. The method involved building a template using a desktop 3D printer and winding of a conducting wire onto it using its printed surface grooves as a guide.

In the theoretical part, we focused on two kinds of coil structures. The first one is so-called polynomial coils. Polynomial coils were not sufficiently investigated in the literature, therefore our study is very novel in that sense. That part of the study consisted of both analytical and FEA calculations. We have shown that, for certain set of parameters, the paraboloid coils provide up to 300-350 ppm of field uniformity. We also investigated solenoidal coils with changing profile. But in that case homogeneity values calculated using FEA were no better than 1000 ppm.

In the next and main part of this thesis work, we focused on spheroidal surface coil structures. We have shown that the spheroidal coils may in fact be a good alternative for generating uniform magnetic fields. Although spheroidal coils were previously proposed in the literature [36-39], no detailed experimental study along with its theoretical background was done so far. In this part of the thesis, we have demonstrated the possibility of generating highly uniform magnetic fields using the spheroidal surface coils in helix form. We briefly introduced the theory of spheroidal surface currents to generate uniform fields inside. Then we derived a parametric winding formula of the spheroidal helical coil for emulating surface currents. This winding reveals in turn to be a discretized version of the magnetic scalar potential of the magnetostatic problem. We also demonstrated our computational results from finite element calculations suggesting that the field uniformity as high as 20 ppm inside almost all volume is available. In the last part, we produced the spheroidal helical coil

by 3D printing using the set of parameters used in the calculations. We measured the magnetic field profile inside of the 3D-printed helical coil using a Hall sensor for the magnetic field. Using these measurements, we determined the level of uniformity, which is fairly promising and finally we discussed our results.

3. POLYNOMIAL COILS

Here we investigated polynomial coil structures of which number of windings gradually increase as a function of vertical distance from the center to the sides. This can be achieved in different ways. We derived formulas for paraboloid, linear and a higher order coil and tried to investigate some design parameters for a better field uniformity.

3.1. Paraboloid Coil Structure

Let's think of a paraboloid coil, having 1000 windings, which is wound on a cylinder of radius $R(z)$ and height h occupying a total volume of $V = 4 \text{ lt}$ ($4 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^3$) (Figure 3.1). The parabola equation for the outside radius of the coil as a function of the coordinate z is: $x = az^2 + b$,

Figure 3.1: The Paraboloid coil.

The volume occupied by the coil may be calculated by integration:

$$V = 2 \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (\pi(az^2 + b)^2 - \pi R^2) dz \quad (3.1)$$

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (a^2 z^4 + 2abz^2 + b^2 - R^2) dz \quad (3.2)$$

Evaluating the integral, we have:

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \left[\frac{a^2}{5} z^5 + \frac{2ab}{3} z^3 + (b^2 - R^2) z \right]_0^{h/2} \quad (3.3)$$

After applying the boundary values

$$\frac{V}{2\pi} = \frac{a^2 h^5}{5 \cdot 2^5} + \frac{2abh^3}{3 \cdot 2^3} + (b^2 - R^2) \frac{h}{2} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\frac{V}{\pi} = \frac{a^2 h^5}{80} + \frac{ah^3}{6} \cdot b + (b^2 - R^2) h \quad (3.5)$$

and rearranging the formula we arrive at an equation which is of second order in b .

$$hb^2 + \frac{ah^3}{6} \cdot b + \left(\frac{a^2 h^5}{80} - R^2 h - \frac{V}{\pi} \right) = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

The Δ of this equation is:

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{ah^3}{6} \right)^2 - 4h \left(\frac{a^2 h^5}{80} - R^2 h - \frac{V}{\pi} \right) \quad (3.7)$$

$$\Delta = \frac{a^2 h^6}{45} + 4R^2 h^2 + \frac{4hV}{\pi} \quad (3.8)$$

Thus, the two roots are:

$$b = \frac{-\left(\frac{ah^3}{6}\right) \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2 \cdot h} \quad (3.9)$$

Here only the first root is physically meaningful thus we have:

$$b = \left(\frac{V}{\pi h} + R^2 - \frac{a^2 h^4}{180} \right)^{1/2} - \frac{ah^2}{12} \quad (3.10)$$

Maximum value of b is assumed when $a = 0$. On the other hand, b must not be smaller than the radius. Thus, we have the inequality:

$$\left(\frac{V}{\pi h} + R^2\right)^{1/2} \geq b \geq R \quad (3.11)$$

to be the form of expected solutions. We have chosen $R = 120 \text{ mm}$ and $h = 437 \text{ mm}$ for our finite element calculations in CST software, for which

$$b_{max} \cong 130,86 \text{ mm} \quad (3.12)$$

$$b_{min} = 120 \text{ mm}$$

values are reached. Thus, a is roughly within the interval $0 \leq a \leq 0.00057 [1/\text{mm}]$.

Equations above were transferred into CST EM Studio parametrically (see Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3) and analysis were performed for 1000 windings and 1 Ampere of current. The axial component of the magnetic field is plotted along the cylindrical axis. Simulations were done for four different parameter pairs (a and b) to find the best set (see Table 3.1).

Figure 3.2: Parametric definition of the problem in CST EM Studio is illustrated.

Figure 3.3: Paraboloid coil defined in CST EM Studio.

Table 3.1: Coil parameters used for simulations in CST.

a [1/mm]	b[mm]
0,00057	120,18
0,00029	125,51
0,00012	128,67
0,00000	130,87

Figure 3.4: Simulation results for different a and b parameter values.

The best magnetic field uniformity has been obtained for $a = 0.00012$ (Figure 3.4). The uniformity is calculated by considering the deviation from the central field value at 50 mm away on both sides which approximately corresponds to $h/10$ value (see Eq. (3.13)).

$$\text{Deviation in 100 mm}(\%) = \frac{B_z(z = 0) - B_z(z = \pm 50 \text{ mm})}{B_z(z = 0)} \times 100 \quad (3.13)$$

In the second step, the simulations were performed for various parameters around the optimal set, that is for the parameter a within the range 0.00009-0.00015 (Table 3.2). The magnetic field uniformity within ± 50 mm range for $a = 0,00012$ values was found to be 0.15%.

Table 3.2: Magnetic field uniformity within ± 50 mm central region.

a [1/mm]	b[mm]	Field Deviation (%)
0.00009	129.22	0.480
0.00010	129.04	0.403
0.00011	128.85	0.261
<u>0.00012</u>	<u>128.67</u>	<u>0.149</u>
0.00013	128.49	0.164
0.00014	128.30	0.431
0.00015	128.12	0.570

3.2. Linearly Changing Coil Structure

Let's suppose we have a linearly increasing winding profile for the coil as we go from center to the sides (see Figure 3.5). In that case, the volume integral over a cylindrical base of height h and radius R can be calculated as follows:

$$V = 2 \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (\pi(az + b)^2 - \pi R^2) dz \quad (3.14)$$

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (a^2 z^2 + 2abz + b^2 - R^2) dz \quad (3.15)$$

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \left[\frac{a^2}{3} z^3 + abz^2 + (b^2 - R^2)z \right]_0^{h/2} \quad (3.16)$$

Figure 3.5: Linearly changing coil profile defined in CST EM Studio.

$$hb^2 + \frac{ah^2}{2} \cdot b + \left(\frac{a^2 h^3}{12} - R^2 h - \frac{V}{\pi} \right) = 0 \quad (3.17)$$

From here like in the previous derivation:

$$b = \left(\frac{V}{\pi h} + R^2 - \frac{a^2 h^2}{48} \right)^{1/2} - \frac{ah}{4} \quad (3.18)$$

$$\left(\frac{V}{\pi h} + R^2 \right)^{1/2} \geq b \geq R \quad (3.19)$$

The parameter a takes values roughly within the interval $0 \leq a \leq 0.091$ [1/mm] according to Eq. (3.17). Calculations in CST EM Studio using the same number of turns and current value for the parameters listed in Table 3.3 were performed (Figure 3.6), and the magnetic field component along the cylindrical axis was calculated.

It can be inferred from the graph (Figure 3.6) that for $a = 0.018$ one has the smoothest behavior. Field uniformity within ± 50 mm range ($\sim h/10$) is then calculated to be as given in the Table 3.4.

Table 3.3: Winding parameters.

A	b[mm]
0.010	129.70
0.018	128.76
0.025	127.94
0.030	127.35

Figure 3.6: Simulation results for different parameters.

Table 3.4: Magnetic field uniformity within ± 50 mm central region.

a [1/mm]	b[mm]	Field Deviation (%)
0.018	128.76	0.141

The uniformity value calculated for this structure is nearly the same with that of the previous structure.

3.3. General Solution

One can also try to calculate a model with a more general form, $x = az^n + b$ for the outside radius function. That is nothing but inserting an extra degree of freedom (*i.e.* degree of z) to tune for a better homogeneity of the field. One may go through similar calculations, which have been shown in previous two sections:

$$V = 2 \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (\pi(az^n + b)^2 - \pi R^2) dz \quad (3.20)$$

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \int_0^{h/2} (a^2 z^{2n} + 2abz^n + b^2 - R^2) dz \quad (3.21)$$

$$V = 2\pi \cdot \left[\frac{a^2}{2n+1} z^{2n+1} + 2ab \frac{z^{n+1}}{n+1} + (b^2 - R^2)z \right]_0^{h/2} \quad (3.22)$$

$$\frac{h^{2n+1}}{2^{2n}(2n+1)} \cdot a^2 + \frac{bh^{n+1}}{(n+1)2^n} \cdot a + (b^2 - R^2)h - V/\pi = 0 \quad (3.23)$$

The Δ of the equation is:

$$\Delta = \frac{h^{2n+2}}{2^{2n}} \left(\frac{b^2}{(n+1)^2} - \frac{h^{-1}}{2n+1} [(b^2 - R^2)h - V/\pi] \right) \quad (3.24)$$

From here:

$$a = \frac{2^n(2n+1)}{h^n} \left[-\frac{b}{n+1} + \left(\left(\frac{b}{n+1} \right)^2 - \frac{b^2 - R^2 - V/\pi h}{2n+1} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (3.25)$$

We have given the general solution above. Among different combinations of b and n we have tried two specific sets with $n = 12$ and $n = 15$ (see Figure 3.7 and Table 3.5), since these are the best candidates among several other trials.

Table 3.5: Coil parameters and corresponding field deviations.

N	b[mm]	Field Deviation (%)
12	128,3	0,035
15	128,4	0,267

Figure 3.7: Results for parameters $n=12$ and $n=15$ are shown.

These results show that maximum uniformity for polynomial coils is given by the formula $x = az^n + b$, and is attained for $n = 12$ and $b = 128.3$ parameters. The field deviation from uniformity is equal to 350 ppm within $h/10$ range. A stricter optimization procedure may produce even better results. However, construction of such a coil is not feasible and easy in many practical cases. Therefore, we decided to continue our search for uniform magnetic field systems with other structures, which are more appropriate for practical realization. These are the solenoidal coils, consisting of several sections, each wound by stripe conductor, and containing also compensatory coils or extra turns on their ends (see the next section).

4. SOLENOIDS WITH CHANGING PROFILE

In many practical situations one should construct a magnetic system which both generates uniform magnetic field and is easy to manufacture. Traditionally the solenoidal coils are the foremost preferred designs, since they are relatively easier to materialize. These solenoids contain special compensatory coils or extra turns on their ends for reaching higher magnetic field uniformity. An alternative approach is to design such a system that partially implements the approach tried in the previous chapter. That is the outside winding diameter increases towards the two solenoid ends. Besides, in many cases these solenoids are constructed to be wound by stripe conductors. Therefore, they are built consisting of several sections, each for concentric turns of stripe conductors, separating resistive magnets by empty space for a better cooling.

4.1. Solenoid with Compensation Coils at the Ends

One can design a solenoidal system with compensation towards its ends to reach a certain field uniformity. In our study, we analyzed various solenoidal configurations with coils having larger outside diameters for compensating the cylindrical truncation effect at the ends. This principle, based on extra coils or additional windings at the two ends of a solenoid, is well known and routinely used in many practical designs of magnetic systems. As a starting point for such a model, we simulated a system proposed by MRI department of Kazan Physical-Technical Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences (Tatarstan, Russian Federation). The model was expected to maintain a 10^{-4} field uniformity within a central 100 mm diameter sphere (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1: The sketch of the solenoid with compensation coils at the ends.

Figure 4.2: Multi-coil geometry.

Using the dimensions given in Figure 4.1, the sketch (Figure 4.2) and the parametrization of the problem was performed as follows (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3: The Multi-coil and the parametrization in CST Studio.

The resulting magnetic field lines and magnetic field profile on the cylindrical axis can be seen in Figure 4.4 and Figure 4.5 respectively.

Figure 4.4: Resultant magnetic field lines of the structure.

Figure 4.5: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the coil is plotted.

The results of FEA calculation revealed a noticeable field distortions at the two ends of the system analyzed. The field homogeneity in the 100-mm zone in the middle in both axial and radial directions was studied in more details in Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.6: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.

Figure 4.7: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis.

It is obvious that deviations for both directions (axial and radial) are on the order of 1000 ppm (see Table 4.1). Thus, this magnetic system does not provide a magnetic field with the targeted level of uniformity. In order to obtain a higher uniformity level, two alternative structures were also studied below.

Table 4.1: Axial and radial magnetic field homogeneity.

Direction	Magnetic Field Deviation (%)
Axial	0,25
Radial	0,11

4.2. Discrete Solenoids with Changing Outside Diameters

We proposed to construct a solenoid of which outside diameter changes in such manner that the magnetic field inside is uniform in a region as large as possible. The main difference between this design and the case of a polynomial coil analyzed in the previous chapter is that, this case corresponds to a discrete structure, which can be made out of sections particularly designed to employ conductors of rectangular cross-section (i.e. stripe conductor). The calculations for two various designs each having 28 windings was performed. Visual Basic-based macros were written for quick realization of both current and future designs (the text of the macro is given in Appendix B).

4.2.1. Discrete Solenoid: Design 1

In this design, it is assumed that coils having 12 mm width and 5 mm spacing is wound on a 120-mm radius cylindrical template. Number of windings in each coil are proportional to numbers given in Table 4.2. The resulting sketch can be seen in Figure 4.8. The coil would look like the Solidworks model seen in Figure 4.9. The definition of the problem in CST studio can be seen in Figure 4.10 . The resultant magnetic field lines (Figure 4.11) and the magnetic field profiles (Figures 4.12-4.14) can be seen in respective figures.

Table 4.2: Design 1, windings.

wind(1)	wind(2)	wind(3)	wind(4)	wind(5)	wind(6)	wind(7)
12	12	13.5	12	10.5	10.5	10.5
wind(8)	wind(9)	wind(10)	wind(11)	wind(12)	wind(13)	wind(14)
12	12	12	24	27	28.5	30

Figure 4.8: The coil sketch of Design 1.

Figure 4.9: Coil model of Design 1 in Solidworks.

Figure 4.10: The definition of the problem in CST Studio (Design 1).

Figure 4.11: The resulting magnetic field lines in Design 1.

Figure 4.12: The magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted.

Figure 4.13: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.

Figure 4.14: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis

Figure 4.13 and Figure 4.14 reveals that this magnetic system is not appropriate for creation of the magnetic field with high level of uniformity, since the calculated level of uniformity is just %0.31. For that reason, we modelled another design (see below).

4.2.2. Discrete Solenoid: Design 2

In this design, it is assumed that coils having 12 mm width and 5 mm spacing is wound on a 103-mm radius cylindrical template. Number of windings in each coil are

proportional to numbers given in Table 4.3. The resulting sketch can be seen in Figure 4.15. The coil would look like the Solidworks model given in Figure 4.16. The definition of the problem in CST studio can be seen in Figure 4.17. The resultant magnetic field lines (Figure 4.18) and the magnetic field profiles (Figures 4.19-43.21) can be seen in respective figures.

Table 4.3: Design 2, windings.

wind(1)	wind(2)	wind(3)	wind(4)	wind(5)	wind(6)	wind(7)
13.5	15	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5	13.5
wind(8)	wind(9)	wind(10)	wind(11)	wind(12)	wind(13)	wind(14)
13.5	13.5	13.5	15	33	33	33

Figure 4.15: The coil sketch of Design 2.

Figure 4.16: Coil model of Design 2 in Solidworks.

Figure 4.17: The definition of the problem in CST Studio (Design 2).

Figure 4.18: The resulting magnetic field lines in Design 2.

Figure 4.19: The magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted.

It can be deduced from Figure 4.20 and Figure 4.21 that this system isn't also appropriate for creation of a magnetic field with high level of uniformity, since the calculated level of uniformity is only %0.22.

Figure 4.20: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the main axis.

Figure 4.21: The tangential coefficient of the magnetic field strength along the radial axis.

Like the previously analyzed cases, the magnetic systems of both designs cannot allow us to generate desired high uniform magnetic fields. Both of our models are worse compared to the Kazan model, however one can see that they both have better radial uniformity. Of course, these can be shimmed to make the magnetic field inside much more uniform. But on the other hand, even in this form they have a quite enough uniformity for some applications, such as for time-domain NMR. However, in order to obtain the magnetic field with uniformity required for MRI devices, we decided to proceed in the next chapter with the studies of ellipsoidal (spheroidal) coils (see below).

5. SPHEROIDAL SHELL STRUCTURES

Since it is expected that ellipsoidal bodies could be an appropriate frame for obtaining uniform magnetic fields, we decided to investigate spheroidal and spherical shell structures in more detail to see whether we can attain promising results.

5.1. Spherical Shells

5.1.1. Closed Spherical Shell

Here we consider a fictitious spherical shell, which is 540 mm in the outer diameter and has a 10-mm shell thickness (Figure 5.1). This 2D shell is converted into a 3D shell by rotating it around the central vertical axis. The coil is assumed to be woven inside this shell in a rotating manner and has 10000 windings. The magnetostatic calculations were carried out in CST EM Studio (Figure 5.2) assuming 1 ampere current running through the coil.

Figure 5.1: Schematic description of the Spherical Shell Coil is illustrated. The red straight line indicates the region where we have calculated the field uniformity.

The resultant field lines after FEA calculations are plotted in Figure 5.3. The field uniformity calculated by considering tangential field component on a ± 50 mm central line (the red line in Figure 5.1) using the formula in Eq. (3.13) and the results are plotted in Figure 5.4. It turned out that for a spherical shell the field uniformity even for a limited central region is only around 1%, which ruled out the possibility of using such a structure as a uniform field generator.

Figure 5.2: Parametric definition of Spherical Shell Coil in CST.

Figure 5.3: Magnetic field lines for the Spherical Shell Coil.

Figure 5.4: Calculations showed that magnetic field uniformity is around 1.1 % on the ± 50 mm central line (the red line in Figure 5.1).

5.1.2. Spherical Arc Shell

Apart from the fact that the homogeneity due to a closed spherical shell is not promising, such a structure is not practical either. Homogeneous magnetic field inside the structure must be accessible from outside. For that reason, the definition of a new spherical coil can be done by using a reduced arc, where the arc is truncated from the two poles (here with 20 degrees hence the arc is 140 degrees) ($R = 260$ mm). A second arc is created by just shifting the first one outwards by a thickness parameter ($d = 20$ mm). The two arcs are combined using two parallel lines. The coil is defined by the area circumscribed as it is rotated about the main axis. (Figure 5.5).

Figure 5.5: Schematic description of the spherical arcs, which created a spherical arc shell is illustrated. The red and the green lines are the regions for magnetic field uniformity calculation.

Figure 5.6: Cross-sectional view of the Spherical Arc Shell Coil.

The winding parameters are kept same with the previous calculation (10000 turns and 1 A). The parametric definition of the problem in CST is given in Figure 5.7. The spatial profile of the magnetic field lines generated is shown in Figure 5.8. The central homogeneity of the coil magnetic field can be shown in a contour plot where each contour line corresponds to 400 ppm (Figure 5.9).

Homogeneity for the central 100 mm region was also calculated (see red and green lines in Figure 5.5). These results show a considerably high magnetic field uniformity (40 ppm) for this specific structure (Figure 5.10, Figure 5.11). The reason for this will be revealed later when the theory of spheroidal coils is studied.

Figure 5.7: Parametric definition of Spherical Shell Arc Coil.

Figure 5.8: Magnetic field lines for the Spherical Shell Arc Coil.

Figure 5.9: Magnitude of the magnetic field is plotted on the xy plane. Here the star-like central region corresponds to 400 ppm homogeneity.

Figure 5.10: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.

Figure 5.11: Magnetic field magnitude on the green line in Figure 5.5 is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is around 40 ppm.

Figure 5.12: Magnetic field magnitude along the lateral line passing through the coil center is plotted.

To see if this enhanced uniformity is also valid for the lateral axis, the magnetic field profile was calculated along the lateral axis (perpendicular to the axial line) passing through the center (Figure 5.12) and the homogeneity is deduced (Figure 5.13). Surprisingly, the profile along the lateral axis turns out to be even more homogeneous than that along the central axis.

Figure 5.13: Magnetic field magnitude on the red line in Figure 5.5 is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is around 30 ppm.

5.2. Spheroidal Shells

Here we continue with a more general problem, a spheroid rather than a sphere, to see whether elevated uniformity is also possible for these structures. As in the previous cases, we modeled the magnetostatic problem in CST EM Studio.

5.2.1. Elliptical Shell

Elliptical shell structure is formed by taking an elliptic arc ($R_x = 260$ mm and $R_y = 400$ mm) and shifting it by 20 mm (Figure 5.14). The region in between two arcs is rotated by 360 degrees to form a rotational ellipsoid (a spheroid) and a shell for the current flow. As in the previous cases, windings of 1000 turns and current of 1 A was assumed in the model. Cross-sectional view in CST and the parametric definition of the elliptical slice are given in Figure 5.15 and Figure 5.16.

Figure 5.14: Schematic description of the elliptic shell.

Figure 5.15: Prolate ellipsoidal shell coil cross-section as seen in CST Studio.

Figure 5.16: Parametric definition of the prolate ellipsoidal shell problem.

The spatial distribution of the magnetic field lines is shown in Figure 5.17.

Figure 5.17: Resultant magnetic field lines of the prolate ellipsoidal shell structure.

Figure 5.18: Magnitude of the magnetic field is plotted on the xy plane. Here the star-like central region corresponds to 400 ppm homogeneity.

Figure 5.19: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the prolate ellipsoidal coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.

Figure 5.20: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 40 ppm.

Figure 5.21: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 13 ppm.

Thus, it can be seen that similar to the previous case an enhanced level of the magnetic field uniformity can be obtained in this structure.

5.2.2. Truncated Elliptic Shell (Prolate)

This model is obtained by chopping 40 mm off the upper and lower ends of the above structure. The definitions and results related to the model are given below (Figure 5.22 to Figure 5.26). It is seen that this truncation causes only limited deterioration which effects on the lateral homogeneity.

Figure 5.22: Parametric definition of the truncated prolate ellipsoidal shell problem.

Figure 5.23: Resultant magnetic field lines of the truncated prolate ellipsoidal shell structure.

Figure 5.24: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the prolate ellipsoidal coil is plotted. The magnetic field is very homogeneous in the middle.

Figure 5.25: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 40 ppm.

Figure 5.26: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. The Magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 40 ppm.

5.2.3. Truncated Elliptic Shell (Oblate)

We also studied an oblate structure where $R_x = 260$ mm and $R_y = 200$ mm. The truncation in that case is set to be 14 mm. The definitions and results related to this model are illustrated below (Figure 5.27 - Figure 5.31).

Figure 5.27: Parametric definition of the oblate ellipsoidal shell problem.

Figure 5.28: Resultant magnetic field lines of the oblate ellipsoidal shell structure.

Figure 5.29: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the oblate coil is plotted. The magnetic field is less uniform compared to the prolate structure.

Figure 5.30: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted (the green line in Figure 5.14). The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 150 ppm.

Figure 5.31: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis (perpendicular to the major axis, the red line in Figure 5.14) is plotted. Magnetic field homogeneity was calculated to be 360 ppm.

We see that oblate structure is less promising. This is partly because of the enhanced sensitivity to truncation.

5.2.4. Truncated Concentric-Ellipsoidal Shell

A concentric-ellipsoidal shell is defined using two concentric ellipses. The first ellipse is defined by the parameters R_x and R_y , and the second ellipse is by $R_x + d$ and $R_y + d$. The main purpose to study such a double ellipse structure is to compare it with an ellipsoidal shell obtained by shifting a single ellipse (defined by the parameters R_x

and R_y only, See Section 5.2.1). Comparison of the results for these structures showed that the ellipsoidal shell prepared by shifting a single ellipse has a superior magnetic field uniformity. Detailed analysis, which have been omitted here, also revealed that the uniformity of magnetic field in the concentric-ellipsoidal shell (Figure 5.32 - Figure 5.36) is more susceptible to truncation compared to that of an elliptical shell. In addition to that, building such a coil would be more challenging as well.

Figure 5.32: Parametric definition of the concentric-ellipsoidal shell problem.

Figure 5.33: The resultant magnetic field lines of the concentric-ellipsoidal shell structure.

Figure 5.34: Magnetic field magnitude along the major axis of the concentric-ellipsoidal structure.

Figure 5.35: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm line on the major axis is plotted. The magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be around 187 ppm.

Figure 5.36: Magnetic field magnitude along the ± 50 mm lateral line on the minor axis is plotted. Magnetic field homogeneity is calculated to be 422 ppm.

6. SPHEROIDAL COILS

Spheroidal and spherical structures can be used to maintain uniform fields in case certain surface currents are maintained. For that, one needs to make certain surface coil structures. In this part of our study, we start with some analytical calculations which provide the theory. Essentially, we demonstrate the possibility of generating uniform magnetic fields by means of spheroidal surface coils. For that, we have developed a theoretical model, which formulates the necessary coil structures. We performed finite element analysis (FEA) calculations of this magnetostatic problem using the formulation with certain set of parameters to confirm these derivations. Our results from calculations suggests that, uniformity of at least 200 ppm within 75% of whole spheroidal volume and 500 ppm uniformity within 90% of it are in fact achievable. We then proposed a helical structure, which can be materialized as an air-cored spheroidal coil. Computer aided design (CAD) of a coil template was made using the formulations we have derived. For producing the template; a commercial off the shelf, affordable, desktop 3D printer was employed, since it is virtually impossible via conventional production techniques. After the winding was performed over the template, the coil was driven by a current source and magnetic field inside was measured using a Hall probe through holes of the template, which have been intentionally left during the CAD process. Our measurements are in good agreement with the finite element results, which show a highly uniform magnetic field therein.

6.1. Surface Current Density for a Uniform Field therein

In order to find a surface current density profile which yields to a uniform magnetic field inside an ellipsoid, we start with the definition of a so-called “current function” (ϕ), asserted by Marsh [41] using the exactness of the differential in the time-independent equation of continuity ($\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{j} = 0$). The relation between this current function and the surface current density (\vec{j}) for a general closed surface was stated to be:

$$\vec{j} = \vec{\nabla}\phi \times \hat{n} \quad (6.1)$$

where \hat{n} is the surface normal pointing outwards. Marsh then showed that indeed a uniform magnetic field is obtainable inside a general ellipsoid using a linear current function³ ($\phi = Kz$) along its major axis⁴. He then showed that for the degenerate case of a spheroid, this approximately corresponds to a discrete winding that obeys a constant ampere per turn ratio along its major axis.

At this point, we turn to a more general problem described by Laslett [40]. Laslett discussed how to find a surface current distribution on a closed surface to generate a stationary magnetic field inside, which is equivalent to that of an outer source. Starting from the time-independent Maxwell equations for magnetic fields ($\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{H} = 0$, $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = \vec{j}$), he used a two-fold gauge transformation. Consequently, he showed that a surface current, for raising such a magnetic field, would be expressed by a surface distribution of the form⁵:

$$\vec{j} = \vec{H} \times \hat{n} \quad (6.2)$$

By comparing Eqs. (6.1) and (6.2), one can see that the current function is actually equal to the magnetic scalar potential apart from a minus sign ($\vec{H} = \vec{\nabla}\phi = -\vec{\nabla}\Phi_{scalar}$). So, we can conclude that, what Marsh [41] called a “current function” is actually, minus the magnetic scalar potential function. Thus, in case the curl of the magnetic field is zero (no currents inside), one can always define such a potential that obeys the Laplace equation which can always be solved using appropriate boundary conditions.

In fact, Živaljevič and Aleksič [61] approached the problem of generating uniform magnetic fields inside of prolate and oblate spheroidal surfaces in this manner. They used the regular relation $\vec{H} = -\vec{\nabla}\Phi_{scalar}$, and they derived the expressions for the surface current density. For the prolate case for instance, they came up with the result for the current density profile:

$$j = j_o \sin\nu/h \quad (6.3)$$

³ The original current function in the publication is $\phi = -Kz$, which led to a magnetic field alignment along the negative z direction [41].

⁴ Major axis is taken to be the z-axis throughout this article without loss of generality.

⁵ Here the $1/4\pi$ factor in the original paper is omitted since CGS units are employed, such that the Ampère’s Law is stated as $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{H} = 4\pi\vec{j}$ [29].

where j_o is a positive constant, v is the elevation coordinate among prolate spheroidal coordinates (u, v, ϕ) , and h is the Lamé coefficient therein (see Appendix C).

Although the result in Eq. (6.3) did not say much about the actual winding of a coil, it can be shown to reproduce the current function indicated by Marsh [41]. Hence, the derivation by Živaljević and Aleksić [61] can be integrated with the well-known result of constant ampere per turn ratio [62].

To demonstrate one points out that, in order the current profile in Eq. (6.3) to yield a magnetic field aligned along the positive z-axis⁶;

$$\vec{H} = H_o \hat{z} \quad (6.4)$$

it must adopt the vector form:

$$\vec{j} = \frac{j_o}{h} \sin v \hat{\phi} \quad (6.5)$$

Marsh's current function (in its positive form, $\phi = Kz$) can be converted into the prolate spheroidal coordinates as follows⁷:

$$\phi = Kz = Kc \cosh u_o \cos v = Ka \cos v \quad (6.6)$$

where, u is replaced by u_o since the surface is of a certain spheroid. Inserting Eq. (6.6) into Eq. (6.1) one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{j} &= \vec{\nabla} \phi \times \hat{n} = Kc \cosh u_o \vec{\nabla}(\cos v) \times \hat{u} \\ &= Ka \frac{1}{h} \frac{\partial \cos v}{\partial v} \hat{v} \times \hat{u} \\ &= \frac{Ka}{h} \sin v \hat{\phi} \end{aligned} \quad (6.7)$$

Here Eq. (C1.3) is utilized and \hat{n} is replaced by \hat{u} . Setting $j_o \equiv Ka$, one can reach at the surface current density in Eq. (6.5). Thus, the derivation by Živaljević and Aleksić [61] is confirmed to bring about the same constant ampere per turn ratio result.

Going back to Eq. (6.6) one can see that the current function can be expressed

⁶ A detailed derivation can also be followed in [24].

⁷ See Appendix C.

as:

$$\phi = j_o \cos v \quad (6.8)$$

Using the fact that $\vec{H} = \vec{\nabla}\phi$, it is possible to return to the current function using the homogeneity constraint since:

$$\vec{H} = H_o \hat{z} = \vec{\nabla}\phi = \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial z} \hat{z} \quad (6.9)$$

$$\Rightarrow \phi \propto z$$

satisfying the linear current function in Eq. (6.6). Thus, one can see that Eqs. (6.1), (6.2) and (6.3) (which are all taken from different articles [40, 41, 61]), are proven to be consistent within themselves.

6.2. Current Rings

In order to confirm the uniformity prerequisite “constant ampere per turns per unit length along the z axis”, we performed a FEA calculation using CST EM Studio. Here we imagine one hundred current carrying rings of which circumferences follow the surface of a spheroid having dimensions $a = 320 \text{ mm}$ and $b = 160 \text{ mm}$ (Figure 6.1-Figure 6.2). 1 ampere current was assumed to circulate on each ring (Figure 6.3). The rings were taken to be of copper wires 0.9 mm in diameter. Simulation results are plotted for the lengths along the principal (z) and a lateral axis (which can be taken as x axis without loss of generality). The structural view and a cross-sectional view of a few meshed wires can be seen in Figure 6.3. Our FEA results along principle and lateral axes are given in Figure 6.4 and Figure 6.5, respectively. Field uniformities along both axes are found to be 0.03% (300 ppm).

Figure 6.1: a) The spheroid dimensions and b) the axes.

Figure 6.2: The current carrying rings on a prolate spheroid is illustrated.

Figure 6.3: a) The spheroidal surface current rings structure modeled in CST EM Studio. Small arrows indicated the direction of the current. b) Cross-sectional view of the meshed structure is on the right.

Figure 6.4: Magnetic field along the principal axis., Field uniformity = 0.03%.

Figure 6.5: Magnetic field along the lateral axis, Field uniformity = 0.03%.

Since there must exist input and output junctions for the current to flow, open ring structures progressively soldered to each other were proposed in the previous works [44, 46]. However, these works were addressing relatively large structures where the effects due to soldered joints and jumper connections between rings were negligible. This method would considerably affect magnetic field uniformity in smaller structures [60].

6.3. The Winding Function

In order to emulate a constant ampere per turn ratio as exact as possible using a discrete winding, a constant pitch helical spheroidal surface coil formula must be

derived (See Figure 6.6). This formula was already proposed elsewhere, however no exact derivation was given [60].

Figure 6.6: Constant pitch spheroidal surface coil, the spheroid geometry and the spheroidal formula in cylindrical coordinate system.

For deriving a helical formula, one should consider that φ – the azimuthal angle – must repeat itself for every step of the pitch, d ; where $x = r \cos \varphi$ and $y = r \sin \varphi$ in the cylindrical coordinates. Consequently, one may infer that: $\varphi = 2\pi z/d$, and inserting $d = 2a/N$, we obtain the expression for the azimuthal angle:

$$\varphi = \frac{N\pi z}{a} \quad (6.11)$$

for N being the total number of windings. Using Eqs. (6.10) and (6.11), one may deduce the parametric formula for the spheroidal helical coil in Cartesian coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= b \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{a^2}\right)^{1/2} \cos \frac{N\pi z}{a} \\ y &= b \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{a^2}\right)^{1/2} \sin \frac{N\pi z}{a} \end{aligned} \quad (6.12)$$

for $-a < z < a$.

Using the Appendix C and Eq. (6.11), the formula in prolate spheroidal coordinates (u, v, φ) turned out to be much simpler:

$$\varphi = \frac{N\pi c \cosh u_o \cos v}{a} \quad (6.13)$$

$$\varphi = N\pi \cos v \quad \text{for} \quad 0 < v < \pi, \quad u = u_o.$$

which is proportional to Eq. (6.8) up to a constant. One should expect this winding function is emulating a continuous surface current in the case that N is large enough.

One is also free to use this same method for the case of a spherical winding function. For that we are going to restate the formula in Eq. (6.13), for a spherical surface coil having radius R ,

$$\varphi = N\pi \cos\theta \quad \text{for} \quad 0 < \theta < \pi, \quad r = R. \quad (6.14)$$

for (r, θ, φ) being the spherical coordinate variables.

We can further proceed to derive the surface current density function. Since φ angle here, is proportional to the current function (which is discussed above), one may express this relation as $\phi = \alpha\varphi$. Using (6.1), we then write down the surface current as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{j} &= \vec{\nabla}\phi \times \hat{n} = \alpha N\pi \vec{\nabla}(\cos\theta) \times \hat{r} \\ &= \alpha N\pi \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial \cos\theta}{\partial \theta} \hat{\theta} \times \hat{r} \\ &= \frac{\alpha N\pi}{R} \sin\theta \hat{\phi} \end{aligned} \quad (6.15)$$

Comparing this with the result of Haus and Melcher [49], we may deduce that $\alpha = J/2\pi$ (J being the current) to have:

$$\vec{j} = \frac{N}{2R} J \sin\theta \hat{\phi} \quad (6.16)$$

for a spherical surface coil.

Here with the help of this, we may determine the simple and important relation between the winding function (φ), the current function (ϕ) and the scalar magnetic potential (Φ_{scalar}) to be:

$$\varphi = \frac{2\pi}{J} \phi = -\frac{2\pi}{J} \Phi_{scalar} \quad (6.17)$$

Thus, one can easily arrive at a winding function solution by just finding the solution to the Laplace equation using a scalar magnetic potential.

Considering the prolate case, using Eq. (6.17) along with Eq. (6.6) we may record:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi = \frac{2\pi}{J} \phi &= \frac{2\pi K a}{J} \cos v \\ &= \frac{N\pi K d}{J} \cos v \end{aligned} \quad (6.18)$$

Comparing Eq. (6.18) with Eq. (6.13), it is seen that K in the current function is:

$$K = J/d \quad (6.19)$$

for a discrete current distribution, which is in Ampere per length units.

6.4. The Spheroidal Helical Coil

To confirm the parametric formula demonstrated in (6.12), we performed a finite element calculation using CST EM Studio simulation software. We solved the magnetostatic problem of a spheroidal surface coil defined using the parameters: $a = 75 \text{ mm}$, $b = 50 \text{ mm}$, $N = 100$, which is driven by a coil current of 1.6 Ampere. The physical center of the spheroid is the origin and a current path to complete the current circulation is defined in a way to circumvent the coil itself, and to be wide enough not to cause any influence on the field inside (Figure 6.7a). The solution domain in CST approach was taken large enough (600 mm free space in all directions) to minimize the effects from the boundaries. The boundaries were accepted to be magnetic for which all tangential components of magnetic field are taken to be zero (Figure 6.7b, Figure 6.8a). Calculations for different mesh combinations in CST were carried out for the parameters above. The results presented here belong to those obtained with an adaptive mesh algorithm, which in turn resulted in a tetrahedral mesh of 312,062 tetrahedrons (Figure 6.8b), which was enough for describing the problem.

Figure 6.9 shows the resultant magnetic field lines in yz plane (it is same for xz

plane). Here one can see a highly linear magnetic field, although it is hard to determine the level of homogeneity from this figure. In order to see a quantitative picture, we plot the field along the major and minor axes respectively in Figure 6.10 and Figure 6.11. One can see a good linear behavior and a clear alignment along the major axis. That is because the lateral component is nearly vanishing along with the homogeneity of the major component.

Figure 6.7: The magnetostatic problem in CST EM Studio: a) The helical spheroidal coil and the current path for the flow. The path is ranging between ± 250 mm in z , and between 0-250 mm in y directions. b) The computational region is selected to be large enough to minimize the effects from the boundaries.

Figure 6.8: 2-dimensional view of the problem is illustrated. Construction of the magnetostatic problem in CST EM Studio: a) The helical spheroidal coil, the current path and the boundaries. b) The mesh structure used in the problem is tetrahedral and contains 312,062 tetrahedrons which are demonstrated here.

Figure 6.9: Magnetic field plotted in the yz plane (units are in Tesla ($V.s/m^2$)).

Magnitudes of the magnetic field on the xy, xz and yz planes are plotted in Figure 6.12. Here each step in the color ramp means a 0.0001 mT field change, which then corresponds to 0.01% (100 ppm) field uniformity within a single color. It is seen that roughly 75% of the internal volume assumed 0.02% (200 ppm) of field uniformity, whereas considering 90% of the volume it is 0.05% (500 ppm).

Figure 6.10: The three components of the magnetic field along the major axis.

Figure 6.11: The three components of the magnetic field along one of the minor axes.

It is clear that, a finer pitch would result in a higher uniformity and vice versa. Therefore, the question “How wide a pitch can be?” comes to mind, whereas a certain level of uniformity is still preserved. Our calculations – which we do not show here – suggested that; the pitch must be determined according to the smaller axis, whether the spheroid is a prolate or an oblate structure. As a rule of thumb, the pitch size must not exceed one tenth of the whole size of the minor axis ($2b$) in order not to have the field uniformity poorer than 0.1% (1000 ppm).

Figure 6.12: Magnetic field uniformity in the a) xy b) xz and c) yz planes.

7. DESIGN AND PRODUCTION

Analysis of the results of our theoretical study inspired us to choose a spheroidal helical coil for developing a laboratory-size uniform magnetic field generator, which can be used in various applications, including magnetic resonance imaging. As a first step a preliminary design was made using *BS Solidworks* software (Figure 7.1). In this design, the device was required to have a hollow geometry and bear some lateral and axial holes for probing and sample placing purposes. The device, fed by a current source, can generate a uniform magnetic field inside, with a strength depending on the magnitude of the current (Figure 7.2).

Figure 7.1: A cross-sectional view of a lab-size spheroidal helical coil designed in *BS Solidworks* software.

Figure 7.2: A general view of a lab-size uniform magnetic field generator.

For producing a helical spheroidal surface coil with the parameters ($a = 75 \text{ mm}$, $b = 50 \text{ mm}$, $N = 100$) we have used in the simulations, a 3D printing method has been adopted. Firstly, a template for supporting the coil has been designed in Solidworks (Figure 7.3) using the parametric formula in Eq.(6.12) to sketch a helical guiding groove on the surface of the spheroid. The template has been designed in two halves (semi-spheroids) of hollow geometry having 3 mm wall thickness. Each semi-spheroid has been designed to have 9 holes on each half (totally 18) through which the magnetic field measurements to be performed.

A *Builder*TM 3D printer was employed for the spheroid production⁸ (Figure 7.4). This printer utilizes the Fused Deposition Molding (FDM) technology in which a polymer filament is melted out of a nozzle to construct the body out of small voxels. FDM method is accurate enough for producing such a template since it can provide up to 100 μm of shape resolution (Figure 7.5 - Drawing are taken from [63]).

⁸ <http://builder3dprinters.com/products/builder-dual-feed-overview/>

Figure 7.3: a) The template designed in Solidworks b) A cross-sectional view of the template c) & d) An illustration of the process of copper wire winding on the template.

After the template was printed, a circular cross-section 0.6 mm enameled copper wire has been wound on it. Total length of the wire was about 25 meters. After the winding, the coil has been covered with a transparent wax to stabilize the structure. The coil is designed to consist of two halves. Electrical contact between upper and the lower halves is maintained by using a pair of beryllium copper contact gasket segment on each side (Figure 7.6).

Figure 7.4: 3D Builder.

Figure 7.5: 3D printing technique based on fused deposition molding (FDM): 1 – Plastic filament is ejected molten from the nozzle, 2 – Material is deposited, 3 – Below there is a controlled movable table to control the material deposition.

Figure 7.6: a) The two semi-spheroids of the template, printed using FDM method: b) The wire wound on the two parts of the template, the contact gasket between the pieces is shown in the inset; c) & d) Assembled spheroidal helical surface coil.

8. MEASUREMENTS

8.1. Method

The magnetic measurements was performed using a *Hirst GM05 Gaussmeter* with its transverse Hall probe (*TP002*), through the holes of the coil template (see Figure 8.1 & Figure 8.2). Current to the coil was fed by a *GW Instek GPS 4303 DC power supply*. The amount of the current was set to 1.61 A for supporting 1 mT field strength [64].

Figure 8.1: The measurement setup of the spheroidal helical surface coil, consisting of a *Hirst GM05 Gaussmeter* and *GW Instek GPS 4303 DC power supply*, is shown. Measurements are done through the holes of the coil template using the transverse Hall probe of the gaussmeter.

Figure 8.2: A closer view of the setup.

8.2. Results and Discussion

Magnetic measurements along the major axis are displayed in Figure 8.3 [64]. Here an overall uniformity of 1.5% is observed. The measured uniformity is lower than expected, first of all, due to large relative error of the gaussmeter used (*Hirst GM05 Gaussmeter*). Besides, an effect of very slight difference in the pitches between the two semi-spheroids is also possible. In addition, the junction between the two semi-spheroids is not optimized to maintain a high level of uniformity. A potential possibility of obtaining much better uniformity is obvious from the magnetic field measurements inside in the lateral direction (Figure 8.4). It is seen that there is an asymmetry in the magnetic field profile between the upper and the lower semi-spheroids. It may appear because of a slight axial misalignment. It is expected that a uniformity of an order of magnitude better than obtained with this very simple setup is feasible if all elements of the spheroidal helical surface coil system are optimized.

Figure 8.3: Magnetic field measurements inside the spheroidal coil along the major axis.

Figure 8.4: Magnetic field measurements inside the spheroidal coil in the lateral direction.

Field strength in such a coil is directly proportional to the amount of current one can supply. Here we see a current to field ratio of about 1600 Amperes per Tesla. Certainly, the maximum field strength achievable is directly dependent on the amount of current the coil can tolerate. A 0.6 mm copper wire has approximately a 0.3 mm^2 cross-sectional area and can handle up to 7-8 Amperes in a single layer coil without overheating [65]. Thus, it is possible to have a maximum of 5 mT (50 Gauss) field strength within this coil. To have higher field strengths, one should go either for a thicker wire – which may in turn require larger spheroids to wind – or use a superconducting wire. On the other hand, a single semi-spheroid of the developed helical coil could be employed as the RF probe in MRI experiments. In this case, the requirements, for RF field uniformity are much softer than for DC magnetic fields.

Thus, we have shown that 3D printing methods can be employed for the production of spheroidal or spherical coils. They are also very prospective for a wide range of applications: ranging from those require practical solutions to those that demand precise experimental setup, in expense of time and funding expended. In fact, there is no theoretical upper limit for improving the homogeneity of the field inside an ideally performed surface current density. Of course, realization of such a surface spheroidal coil with a very uniform magnetic field is not easily attainable experimentally. However, it is obvious that there is room to improve the design of a developed spheroidal surface coil. For instance, the construction can be easily modified to exclude misalignment issues and to apply more precise machining.

9. CONCLUSION

In this thesis work, generation of uniform magnetic fields through utilization of different methods have been investigated theoretically and experimentally. Several different structures, such as polynomial coils, solenoidal coils with edge compensation, spheroidal shell structures and spheroidal helical coils have been studied. We have concluded that, spheroidal surfaces, which are revealed in theoretical analysis, and later confirmed by FEA results, looks very promising from practical applications point of view. Firstly, a constant ampere per turn ratio along the principle axis of a spheroid was studied for uniform magnetic field generation therein. Later, a continuous winding structure, which is easier to realize in practice, – a spheroidal helical coil – has been proposed and was modelled by FEA calculations. Finally, a production method has been proposed, applied and experimental measurements was conducted on a prototype. The measurements were in satisfactory agreement with the results of FEA calculations.

By working on a concrete example, the possibility of employing 3D printing methods for realizing special coil structures for different applications have been proven as well. Here, in this specific example, a spheroidal surface coil has been manufactured for uniform magnetic field generation, but the method is readily applicable for any other kind of specific coil structure. We have achieved a field uniformity of around 1% experimentally, although numerical analysis pointed out the possibility of 20 ppm uniformity. The measured uniformity is lower than expected probably due to some reasons. These may be; large relative error of the Hall probe equipment, slight difference in the pitches between the two semi-spheroids, not-optimal junction between two semi-spheroids and slight axial misalignment of two halves of the helical spheroid coil system. It is obvious that there is room to improve the design of developed spheroidal surface coil. The experimental results were promising and we believe that they can be much improved through an accurate manufacturing process.

REFERENCES

- [1] Machintyre S., (1999), “The Measurement, Instrumentation, and Sensors Handbook, Chapter 48: Magnetic Field Measurement”, 1st Edition, CRC Press LLC.
- [2] Fernández-García M. P., Teixeira J. M., Machado P., Oliveira M. R. F. F., Maia J. M., Pereira C., Pereira A. M., Freire C., Araujo J. P., (2015), “Automatized and desktop AC-susceptometer for the in situ and real time monitoring of magnetic nanoparticles’ synthesis by coprecipitation”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 86 (4), 043904.
- [3] Smith E., Posluszny T., (1986), “Uniform field generating eddy current testing processing method and apparatus”, Design Patent, US Patent: 4594549.
- [4] Bronaugh E. L., (1995), “Helmholtz coils for calibration of probes and sensors: Limits of magnetic field accuracy and uniformity”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE International Symposium on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 72-76, Atlanta, GA, USA, 14-18 August.
- [5] Pahl R. A., Rovey J. L., Pommerenke D. J., (2014), “Comparison of magnetic probe calibration at nano and millitesla magnitudes”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 85 (1), 015112.
- [6] Cornell E. A., Monroe C., Wieman C. E., (1991), “Multiply loaded, ac magnetic trap for neutral atoms”, *Physical Review Letters*, 67 (18), 2439-2442.
- [7] Buxton R. B., (2009), “Introduction to Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging | Principles and Techniques”, Chapter 14, 2nd Edition, 341-367, Cambridge University Press.
- [8] Weishaupt D., Köchli V. D., Marincek B., (2006), “How Does MRI Work?”, 2nd Edition, 41–44, Springer-Verlag.
- [9] Web 1, (2016), <https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:VFPt>, (Accessed: 25/02/2017)
- [10] Purcell E. M., Morin D. J., (2013), “Electricity and Magnetism”, 3rd Edition, 299-300, Cambridge University Press.
- [11] Schill, R. A. Jr., Hoff K., (2001), “Characterizing and calibrating a large Helmholtz coil at low ac magnetic field levels with peak magnitudes below the earth’s magnetic field”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 72 (6), 2769.
- [12] Godínez F. A., Chávez O., Zenit R., (2012), “Note: Design of a novel rotating magnetic field device”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 83 (6), 066109.
- [13] Beiranvand R., (2013), “Analyzing the uniformity of the generated magnetic field by a practical one-dimensional Helmholtz coils system”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 84 (7), 075109.

- [14] Beiranvand R., (2014), “Magnetic field uniformity of the practical tri-axial Helmholtz coils systems”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 85 (5), 055115.
- [15] Spethmann A., Trottenberg T., Kersten H., (2015), “Instrument for spatially resolved simultaneous measurements of forces and currents in particle beams”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 86 (1), 015107.
- [16] Podaru G., Moore J., Dani R. K., Prakash P., Chikan V., (2015), “Nested Helmholtz coil design for producing homogeneous transient rotating magnetic fields”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 86 (3), 034701.
- [17] Abbott J. J., (2015), “Parametric design of tri-axial nested Helmholtz coils”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 86 (5), 054701.
- [18] Web 2, (2016), https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Helmholtz_coils, (Accessed: 10/01/2017)
- [19] Zijlstra H., (1967), “Experimental Methods in Magnetism I”, *Selected Topics in Solid State Physics*, Vol. IX, 1st Edition, 36-38, North-Holland Pub. Co.
- [20] Bell G. B., Marino A. A., (1989), “Exposure systems for production of uniform magnetic fields”, *Journal of Bioelectricity*, 8 (2), 147–158.
- [21] Vanderlinde J., (2004), “Classical Electromagnetic Theory”, 2nd Edition, 111-112, Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publisher.
- [22] Magdaleno-Adame S., Olivares-Galvan J.C., Campero-Littlewood E., Escarela-Perez R., Blanco-Brisset E., (2010), “Coil Systems to Generate Uniform Magnetic Field Volumes”, Excerpt from the Proceedings of the COMSOL Conference, 1-7, Boston, USA, 7-9 October.
- [23] Rubens S. M., (1945), “Cube-surface coil for producing a uniform magnetic field”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 16 (9), 243-245.
- [24] Firester A., (1966), “Design of square helmholtz coil systems”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 37 (9), 1264-1265.
- [25] Merritt R., Purcell C., Stroink G., (1983), “Uniform magnetic field produced by three, four, and five square coils”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 54 (7), 879–882.
- [26] Baker J. R., (1950), “An improved three-coil system for producing a uniform magnetic field”, *Journal of Scientific Instruments*, 27 (7), 197-199.
- [27] Wang J., She S., Zhang S., (2002), “An improved Helmholtz coil and analysis of its magnetic field homogeneity”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 73 (5), 2175–2179.
- [28] Robinson P. R., (1983), “Improvements to the system of four equiradial coils for producing a uniform magnetic field”, *Journal of Physics E: Scientific Instruments*, 16 (1), 39-42.

- [29] Gottardi G., Mesirca P., Agostini C., Remondini D., Bersani F., (2003), “A four coil exposure system (tetracoil) producing a highly uniform magnetic field”, *Bioelectromagnetics*, 24 (2), 125–133.
- [30] Alldred J. C., Scollar I., (1967), “Square cross section coils for the production of uniform magnetic fields”, *Journal of Scientific Instruments*, 44 (9), 755–760.
- [31] Ogay V., Baranov P., Stepankova A., (2014), “Modelling coils system for generating homogeneous magnetic field”, 20th International Conference for Students and Young Scientists: Modern Techniques and Technologies (MTT'2014), IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 66 (1), 012009, Tomsk, Russia, 14–18 April 2014.
- [32] Sasada I., Nakashima Y., (2006), “Planar coil system consisting of three coil pairs for producing a uniform magnetic field”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 99 (8), 08D904.
- [33] Bonetto F., Anoardo E., Polello M., (2006), “Saddle coils for uniform static magnetic field generation in NMR experiments,” *Concepts in Magnetic Resonance Part B*, 29B (1), 9–19.
- [34] Dinale J., Vrbancich J., (2014), “Generation of long prolate volumes of uniform magnetic field in cylindrical saddle-shaped coils”, *Measurement Science and Technology*, 25 (035903), 1–13.
- [35] Ginsberg D. M., Melchner M. J., (1970), “Optimum Geometry of Saddle Shaped Coils for Generating a Uniform Magnetic Field”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 41 (1), 122-123.
- [36] Maxwell J. C., (1892), “A Treatise on Electricity and Magnetism”, 1st Edition, Vol. 2., 62-66, Clarendon.
- [37] Mascart E., Joubert J., (1896), “Leçons sur L'Électricité et le Magnétisme”, 2nd Edition, 545–546, G. Masson Editeur – Gauthier-Villars et Fils.
- [38] Stoner E. C., (1945), “Demagnetizing factors for ellipsoids”, *Philosophical Magazine*, 36 (263), 803–821.
- [39] Osborn J. A., (1945), “Demagnetizing factors of the general ellipsoid”, *Physical Review*, 67 (11-12), 7352–7357.
- [40] Laslett L. J., (1966), “An equivalent distribution of surface currents for the generation of a prescribed static magnetic field within the enclosed volume,” *Journal of Applied Physics*, 37 (6), 2361–2363.
- [41] Marsh G. E., (1975), “Uniform magnetic field in deflection coil design and the problem of ellipsoid”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 46 (7), 3178–3181.
- [42] Blewett J. P., (1947), “Magnetic Field Configurations Due to Air Core Coils”, *Journal of Applied Physics*, 18 (11), 968-976.

- [43] Nouri N., Plaster B., (2013), “Comparison of magnetic field uniformities for discretized and finite-sized standard $\cos\theta$, solenoidal, and spherical coils” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research A*, 723 (1), 30–35.
- [44] Clark J. W., (1938), “A new method for obtaining a uniform magnetic field”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 9 (10), 320–322.
- [45] Caffey T. W. H., (1965), “Fabricating a Spherical Coil”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 36 (1), 103-104.
- [46] Everett J. E., Osemeikhian J. E., (1966), “Spherical coils for uniform magnetic fields,” *Journal of Scientific Instruments*, 43 (7), 470–474.
- [47] Kanazawa K., Arikawa T., (1982), “Uniform magnetic field for perfectron by means of spherical air-core coil”, *Journal of the Mass Spectrometry Society of Japan On-line*, 30 (4), 281–287.
- [48] Primdahl F., Jensen P. A., (1982), “Compact spherical coil for fluxgate magnetometer vector feedback”, *Journal of Physics E: Scientific Instruments* 15 (2), 221-226.
- [49] Haus H. A., Melcher J. R., (1989), “Electromagnetic Fields and Energy”, Sec. 8.5, 1st Edition, 29–34, Prentice-Hall.
- [50] Web 3, (2008), <https://ocw.mit.edu>, License: [Creative Commons BY-NC-SA](#), 8.5.1: [Field and inductance of a spherical coil](#), (Accessed: 13/02/2016).
- [51] Zahn M., (2012), “Uniform magnetic field spherical coil for MRI”, Design Patent, US Patent: 8093896 B2.
- [52] Abele M. G., (2005), “Generation and Confinement of Uniform Magnetic Fields with Surface Currents”, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, 41 (10), 4179-4181.
- [53] Cai X., (1989), “Uniform Magnetic Field Generated by Two Orthogonal Sheet Current Loops”, *IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, 31 (3), 209-217.
- [54] Crow J. T., (1996), “A method for producing highly uniform field characteristic with line currents”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 67 (3), 761-768.
- [55] Abele M. G., (1993), “Structures of Permanent Magnets: Generation of Uniform Fields”, 1st Edition, John Wiley.
- [56] Manz B., Benecke M., Volke F., (2008), “A simple, small and low cost permanent magnet design to produce homogeneous magnetic fields”, *Journal of Magnetic Resonance*, 192 (1), 131-138.
- [57] Sugihara T., Matsui H., Ohira K., Higuchi M., (1964), “A spheroidal coil homogeneous magnetic field β -Ray spectrometer for coincidence and precisionspectroscopy”, *Scientific Reports of Hyogy University of Agriculture*, 6 (1.2), 1–6.

- [58] Antony M. S., Zirnheld J. P., (1983), "Uniform magnetic field due to currents through air-cored ellipsoidal coils", Japanese Journal of Applied Physics, 22 (1), 205.
- [59] Hernandez R., Rodriguez A. O., Salgado P., Barrios F. A., (2003), "Ellipsoidal Coil for Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy", Seventh Mexican Symposium on Medical Physics, AIP Conference Proceedings, 682(1), 205-210, Mexico City, Mexico, 24-26 March.
- [60] Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), "Generation of uniform magnetic field using a spheroidal helical coil structure", 9th International Conference on Magnetic and Superconducting Materials (MSM15), Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 667 (1), 012009, Antalya, Turkey, 30 April-3 May.
- [61] Živaljevič D. U., Aleksič S. R., (2007), "Generating homogeneous magnetostatic field inside prolate and oblate ellipsoidal coil", International Journal of Electronics Communication (AEÜ), 61 (10), 637–644.
- [62] Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2017), "Comment on "Generating homogeneous magnetostatic field inside prolate and oblate ellipsoidal coil"", accepted to International Journal of Electronics and Communication (AEÜ).
- [63] Web 4, (2016), https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/FDM_by_Zureks, (Accessed: 23/11/2016)
- [64] Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), "Note: 3D printed spheroid for uniform magnetic field generation", Review of Scientific Instruments, 87 (10), 106103.
- [65] Kories R., Schmidt-Walter H., (2008), "Taschenbuch der Elektrotechnik: Grundlagen und Elektronik", 641, Verlag Harri Deutsch.
- [66] Arfken G., (1970), "Mathematical methods for physicists", 2nd Edition, 103–108, Academic Press.

BIOGRAPHY

Yavuz Öztürk was graduated from Bilkent University Physics Department in year 2002 and he remained in the same department to earn his master's degree in 2004. He has been working in TÜBİTAK BILGEM as an electromagnetic field measurement specialist and finite element analyst since year 2008. He has been working in various projects with high commitment as a researcher, lab/field tester, calibrator, reporter, finite element analyst.

Yavuz Öztürk is involved in the PhD program at Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences, Gebze Technical University under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Bulat Z. RAMİ. He is still conducting research on special magnetic structures with his supervisor.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Outcome of the Thesis Work

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), “Generation of uniform magnetic field using a spheroidal helical coil structure”, 9th International Conference on Magnetic and Superconducting Materials (MSM15), Journal of Physics: Conference Series, 667 (1), 012009, Antalya, Turkey, 30 April-3 May.

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2017), “Comment on “Generating homogeneous magnetostatic field inside prolate and oblate ellipsoidal coil””, accepted to International Journal of Electronics and Communication (AEÜ).

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), “Note: 3D printed spheroid for uniform magnetic field generation”, Review of Scientific Instruments, 87 (10), 106103.

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), “Obtaining Highly Uniform Magnetic Fields by Utilization of Spheroidal Coils: A study from Theoretical Calculations to Experiment (Talk)”, IPCAP 2016, 25-27 Feb 2016, Erzurum, TURKEY

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2015), “Generation of uniform magnetic field using a spheroidal helical coil structure, 9th International Conference on Magnetic and Superconducting Materials (MSM15) (Poster)”, 1-3 May 2015, Antalya, TURKEY.

Öztürk Y., Aktaş B., (2016), “Doğrusal Artan Manyetik Alan Oluşturmak için Helisel Sarım Yöntemi”, Patent Pending @ Turkish Patent Institute, Application Date: 11/03/2016, Ref: 1332.P.13.

⁹ A Helical Winding Method for Creating Linearly Increasing Magnetic Field

Appendix B: Design Macro for Discrete Solenoids

Table B1.1: Design macro used in CST studio for automatic formation of the coils.

<pre> Dim d, l, shift, R, wind(14), j As Integer DoubleDim i, xN As Integer Dim a,aa As String wind (1) = 13.5 wind (2) = 15 wind (3) = 13.5 wind (4) = 13.5 wind (5) = 13.5 wind (6) = 13.5 wind (7) = 13.5 wind (8) = 13.5 wind (9) = 13.5 wind (10) = 13.5 wind (11) = 15 wind (12) = 33 wind (13) = 33 wind (14) = 33 R = 103 'winding radius d = 12 'winding thickness l = 5 'spacing between windings j = 10 xN = 20 ' winding coefficient WCS.ActivateWCS "global" For i = 1 To 14 shift = (i-1)*(d+l) + l/2 a = "rectangle"& i With Rectangle .Reset .Name a .Curve "curve1" .Xrange shift, shift+d .Yrange R, R+wind(i) .Create End With Next With WCS .SetNormal "1", "0", "0" .SetUVector "0", "1", "0" .ActivateWCS "local" End With </pre>	<pre> 'Drawing Circles For i = 1 To 14 With Circle .Reset .Name "circle" .Curve "curve1" .Radius R .Xcenter "0.0" .Ycenter "0.0" .Segments "0" .Create End With 'Drawing Windings a = "coil"& i aa = "curve1:rectangle" & i With Coil .Reset .Name a .Material "Copper (annealed)" .ProjectProfileToPathAdvanced "True" .ProfileName aa .PathName "curve1:circle" .Current j .Phase "0.0" .NTurns wind(i)*xN .Create End With With Transform .Reset .Name a .Origin "Free" .Center "0", "0", "0" .PlaneNormal "0", "0", "1" .MultipleObjects "True" .GroupObjects "False" .Repetitions "1" .MultipleSelection "False" .MirrorCoil End With Next </pre>
--	--

Appendix C: Prolate Spheroidal Coordinates

The relations between prolate spheroidal and Cartesian coordinates and the Lamé coefficient are as follows (Figure C1.1 is taken from [60])

Figure C1.1: Unit vectors and dimensions in prolate spheroidal coordinates.

$$x = c \sinh u \sin v \cos \varphi \quad (\text{C1.1})$$

$$y = c \sinh u \sin v \sin \varphi \quad (\text{C1.2})$$

$$z = c \cosh u \cos v \quad (\text{C1.3})$$

and

$$h = c(\sinh^2 u + \sin^2 v)^{1/2} \quad (\text{C1.4})$$

where $c = \sqrt{a^2 - b^2}$ for $a > b$, a and b being the spheroidal dimensions [66].